

MATHEMATICS CONCEPT IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL: A BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS

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Abstract. The purpose of this study was to describe the trend and development of research about the mathematics concept in elementary schools in Indonesia. This study was a literature review research using bibliometric analysis. The exploration process of the articles' published results was taken through an open-access website such as google scholar database for the last ten years. The exploration of articles published results used Harzing's Publish or Perish software with the keywords "Konsep Dasar Matematika Sekolah Dasar" and "Mathematics Concept in Elementary School". The results of the exploration process were analyzed by using VOSviewer software for visualization and relationship for all of the research results. This study's results showed there were 1185 articles had been published based on articles exploration criteria. After reducing the data, there were 37 articles with the relevant criteria. The bibliometric analysis results of the relevant articles were the understanding of student mathematics concepts in elementary school, the pre-service students and teacher knowledge about the mathematics concept in elementary school, and the solution for improving students' understanding of mathematics concepts in elementary school.

INTRODUCTION

Education is an important aspect of human life development (Alpian et al., 2019). This happens because education

can facilitate all people to improve their social conditions (Faiz & Kurniawaty, 2022). According to the statement, Alpian et al. (2019) states education plays a major

role in developing competitive human resources. Education in Indonesia has not run optimally (Suliyannah et al., 2021). That statement is supported by Safitri et al. (2022) who state education in Indonesia is not evenly equitable.

Equitable education is a solution to obtaining the best quality education (Nanggala, 2020). This equitable education has to be implemented at all levels of education, especially in elementary school. Education in elementary school is the key to the development of student knowledge for the next level and the achievement of the best quality education (Rahayu, 2015). At this elementary school level, students are introduced to various types of problems in learning all fields, especially mathematics.

Mathematics has an important role in the world of education (Surya, 2019). Based on UU No. 22 the Year 2003, mathematics is a subject that has to be taught from elementary to secondary education. There are still many students who think that mathematics is a difficult subject to learn (Gazali, 2016). The study results by Arindiono & Ramadhani (2013) stated mathematics is considered a difficult subject because it contains many formulas that have to learn and contain contextual problems that are difficult to understand. However, mathematics is important for human life so it needs to be learned and mastered.

The mathematical skills that are becoming the learning goals in elementary school are understanding mathematical concepts, explaining the interrelationships between concepts, and implementing concepts appropriately to solve problems (Hidayat, 2018; Rahmah, 2018).

Understanding mathematical concept is the most important aspect of learning mathematics (Hayati et al., 2019). Based on that statement, Asfar et al. (2019) stated understanding the mathematics concept is important so that students have a solid knowledge for the next learning process. The mathematics concept obtained in elementary school is the provision for student understanding at the next level (Rahmah, 2018). Besides, the best mathematical concept would make it easier for teachers to provide more complex learning materials in the future (Ibrokhimovich et al., 2022).

The understanding of students' mathematical concepts in Indonesia is still low. This statement is evidenced by the Trends of International Mathematics Science Study (TIMSS) results that show Indonesia is in the bottom 6 position (Mullis, Martin, Foy, & Arora, 2015). This condition occurs because students do not understand the problems given so they solve mathematical problems incorrectly (Ghufron et al., 2022). Students still have difficulty in mastering the material because they have a low understanding of

the mathematics concept. (Astuty & Wijayanti, 2013; Dewi & Kusriani, 2014). Fauzan et al. (2013) stated that this low achievement was because students still had difficulty in connecting mathematical concepts with the given contextual problems. Therefore, this study aims to describe trends regarding the development of students' mathematical concepts in elementary school in Indonesia based on the previous research results.

The published research results were analyzed using the bibliometric analysis technique. Bibliometric analysis is an analytical method that is often used in exploring and analyzing data from large-scale scientific research (Donthu, Kumar, Mukherjee, et al., 2021). This bibliometric analysis facilitates the development of research classified in the form of articles, authors, and journals (Merigó & Yang, 2016). Researchers use this bibliometric analysis for various research purposes such as describing trends in the research area, journal performance, research object collaboration, and exploring other research developments (Donthu, Kumar, Pandey, et al., 2021; Verma & Gustafsson, 2020). Therefore, the results of this study are expected to provide recommendations for further research and become an evaluation in learning mathematics in Indonesia, especially in elementary school.

METHOD

This study was a literature review research by focused on the sub-topic of the mathematical concept. A literature review describes the results of published articles that provide information of recent or current literature (Grant & Booth, 2009). The purpose of this study was to describe the trend and development of research publications on the mathematical concept. The exploration process was carried out using Harzing's Publish or Perish software with the limitation for publication in the last 10 years from 2012 to 2022. The data collection was carried out for open-access journals through the Google Scholar database with the keywords "Konsep Dasar Matematika di Sekolah Dasar" and "Mathematics Concept in Elementary School". The steps of this study are presented in Figure 1 (Ahyan et al., 2021; Suliyanah et al., 2021).

Figure 1. Research Steps

Figure 1 shows the stages of bibliometric analysis in this study. In the first stage, the process of determining the keywords aims to have limitations for the research object to be studied. In this study, the research object is the mathematical concept in elementary school. Exploring the keywords is the next step. At this stage, the process of exploring the article publications results is carried out by using Harzing's Publish or Perish software. The article is taken through the open-access Google Scholar database with a limitation of the last 10 years (2012-2022). The exploration results are then stored in the form of. Ris and will be analyzed further. The data analysis process was using VOSviewer software. The purpose of the software implementation is to see the visualization of the relationship between the article's publications results. The final stage of this bibliometric analysis was a discussion of the visualization results and other findings related to research trends regarding the mathematical concept in elementary school.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the article exploration results using Harzing's Publish or Perish software, there were 1185 articles published in Indonesian Journals. The number of articles published each year varies with the type and content of different materials. The following is a diagram of article publications from 2012-

2022 in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Articles Publication Diagram

Figure 2 describes the number of articles publications from 2012 to 2022. In the diagram, it can be seen that most publications occurred in 2018 with 221 published articles. In 2018, there was 1 article with the most citations, namely cited by h157 (39.25 per year). This article was researched by Suraji et al. (2018) regarding the analysis of the ability to understand the student's mathematical concepts and mathematical problem-solving abilities. This study aimed to determine the ability to understand the student's mathematical concepts and mathematical problem-solving. The study result was the ability to understand the student's mathematical concepts and problem-solving is still low, especially in solving contextual problems.

Based on the whole article's exploration results, only 37 articles have been published which are related to each other. Detailed information regarding the exploration of the publication of the article

on the mathematical concept in elementary school in 2012-2022 is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. The results of article’s publication

Result	Keyword “Konsep Matematika di Sekolah Dasar”	Keyword “Mathematics Concept in Elementary School”
Publication Year	2012 – 2022	2012 – 2022
Papers	21	16
Citations	37	30
Citations per Paper	1.76	1.88
Authors per Paper	1.57	1.56
h-index	4	3
g-index	5	5
hI,norm	3	3
hA-index	2	2

Table 1 states that the total number

of citations for publication in Indonesian is higher than publications in the English area. However, viewed from citations per paper, English articles are higher than Indonesian articles. Other results regarding h-index, g-index, hI-norm, and hA-index for both article criteria obtained the same results.

The articles that have been collected are analyzed using VOSviewer software to obtain a visualization. The results visualization of the article’s publications using VOSviewer software is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Articles Visualization Using VOSviewer

In Figure 3, Suryadi is one of the researchers who have a material content relationship with other researchers, namely 7 networks. These results indicate that Suryadi is the most productive writer on students’ mathematical concept topics. Suryadi et al. (2017) formulate alternative

learning designs related to the mathematical concepts, especially on the tangen-circle topic. This idea arose because there were learning obstacles, especially related to epistemological barriers to mathematical concepts. The results of this study also gave birth to 4

types of learning obstacles, namely 1) learning obstacles regarding mathematical concepts and prerequisite materials; 2) learning obstacles regarding the relationship between mathematical concepts; and 4) learning obstacles regarding the problem-solving process. In line with the results of that study, Noto et al. (2019) stated that one of the obstacles for students lies in the process of applying the concept. This condition occurs because students find it difficult to understand the given problem. As a result, the solution to the problem is not appropriate. Noto et al. (2019) added that students with low understanding of mathematical concepts would have difficulty on understanding and expressing definitions, could not implement mathematical notation, and could not implement problem-solving strategies.

In its application, Afgani et al. (2018) formulated an instrument to facilitate the development of understanding of the mathematical concepts for prospective teacher students. This instrument consists of 7 aspects, namely individual concern, social identity, individual personality, view of the future, the effect of others who become role models, the effect of the environment inside or outside the classroom, and view of the mathematics. The application of learning using computer-based media increases students' understanding of

mathematical concepts (Nurjanah et al., 2021). Based on that statement, Ruslan et al. (2017) states that learning by applying a visual learning style makes it easier for students to understand the mathematical concept being taught.

Another researcher who published the most scientific articles was Delima et al. (2018) regarding "the analysis of students' mathematical thinking based on their mathematics self-concept". Delima et al. (2018) stated that students with positive mathematics self-concept have good mathematical thinking skills. The Mann-Whitney U test shows that there was a significant difference in students' mathematical thinking skills with positive mathematical self-concept and negative mathematical self-concept. This mathematical self-concept has a significant relationship with students' mathematics procedural knowledge (Afgani et al., 2019).

Understanding students' mathematical concepts can also be facilitated with learning instruments such as practice questions and assignments. Afriansyah et al. (2020) describe that problem-based questions can improve the understanding of mathematical concepts for prospective teacher students. The competence of teachers in preparing materials and practice questions related to mathematical concepts is still low. This statement is supported by Hasnah et al.

(2018) who state that 1) teacher competency test results are still low; 2) the ability of elementary school teachers in mastering mathematics is still low; and 3) the teacher's understanding of the curriculum is still low. Therefore, it is necessary to carry out workshops on strengthening curriculum development and understanding the mathematical concepts on an ongoing basis so teachers gain experience and can design higher-quality learning (Hasnah et al., 2018; Zainal et al., 2018). In the implementation of this workshop, the interactive-coaching method applied in making teaching tools and strengthening the mathematical concepts for elementary school teachers is efficiently implemented (Zainal et al., 2018). At this stage, trainers and elementary school teachers work together to solve given math problems. Elementary school teachers are also given test questions to determine the development of knowledge and understanding of their mathematical concepts.

CONCLUSION

This study showed that mathematical concept is an important learning subject in the development of students' knowledge. This statement is indicated by the trend of research on this material as many as 1185 published articles. However, there were only 37 studies that were related to each other.

Therefore, the mathematical concept is still an interesting research topic for researchers. The results of the bibliometric analysis stated that there are three aspects of the findings in the publication of articles starting from 2012 to 2022, namely understanding the mathematical concept in elementary school, knowledge of prospective teacher students and teachers about mathematical concepts, and solutions in developing an understanding of mathematical concepts.

For researchers who are interested in researching mathematical concepts, the application of the bibliometric analysis method can be alternative research. This bibliometric analysis facilitates researchers to find out detailed, systematic, and structured analysis information. The researcher hopes that the results of this study will be useful as a reference for other researchers. This research can be developed by expanding the exploration using other open-access websites with the research object of mathematical concepts at the high school level. This bibliometric analysis can be done for other topics as well.

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